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National Food Safety Standard

Pathogen Limits for Food

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1. Scope

This standard provides the indexes for pathogen in foods, limits and testing methods.

This standard applies to pre-packaged foods.

This standard does not apply to canned foods.

2. Principles for implementing the standard

2.1 With or without pathogen limits, the food producers, processors and traders shall take control measures to reduce the pathogen level in foods and the possibility of causing risks.

2.2 After taking samples according to provisions of the GB4789.1, the sample shall be tested according to the testing methods in the Table 1.

3. Index Requirements

Table 1 shall be referred to for the pathogen limits for food.

Table 1 Pathogen Limits for Food

Food Category	Pathogen	Sampling Method and Limits (each sample is /25g or /25mL if not specified)				Testing method	Note
		n	c	m	M		
Meat products Processed meat products Ready-to-eat raw meat products	Salmonella	5	0	0	-	GB4789.4	
	L. Monocytogenes	5	0	0	-	GB4789.30	
	S.aureus	5	1	100 CFU/g	1000 CFU/g	GB4789.10, second method	-
Seafood products Processed seafood Ready-to-eat raw seafood Ready-to-eat algae products	E coli O157:H7	5	0	0	-	GB4789.36	Only applicable to beef products
	Salmonella	5	0	0	-	GB4789.4	
	Vibrio parahaemolyticus	5	1	100MPN/g	1000MPN/g	GB4789.7	-
Ready-to-eat egg products	S.aureus	5	1	100 CFU/g	1000 CFU/g	GB4789.10, second method	
	Salmonella	5	0	0	-	GB4789.4	-
Grain products Processed grain products (including baked) Processed wheat and rice products with fillings Instant wheat and rice products	Salmonella	5	0	0	-	GB4789.	
	S.aureus	5	1	100 CFU/g	1000 CFU/g	GB4789.10, second method	-
	Salmonella	5	0	0	-	GB4789.4	
Instant Bean products Fermented bean products Non-fermented bean products	Salmonella	5	0	0	-	GB4789.4	
	S.aureus	5	1	100 CFU/g	1000 CFU/g	GB4789.10, second method	-
	Salmonella	5	0	0	-	GB4789.4	
Chocolate and cocoa products	Salmonella	5	0	0	-	GB4789.4	
	S.aureus	5	1	100 CFU/g	1000 CFU/g	GB4789.10, second method	-
	Salmonella	5	0	0	-	GB4789.4	
Instant fruit and vegetable products (including preserved vegetables)	S.aureus	5	1	100 CFU/g (mL)	1000 CFU/g	GB4789.10, second method	-
	E coli O157:H7	5	0	0	-	GB4789.36	

Beverages (excluding pre-packaged drinking water and carbonated beverage)	Salmonella	5	0	0	-	GB4789.4	-
	S.aureus	5	1	100 CFU/g (mL)	1000 CFU/g (mL)	GB4789.10, second method	-
Frozen drinks	Salmonella	5	0	0	-	GB4789.4	
	S.aureus	5	1	100 CFU/g (mL)	100 CFU/g (mL)	GB4789.10, second method	-
Instant condiments	Salmonella	5	0	0	-	GB4789.4	
	S.aureus	5	2	100 CFU/g (mL)	1000 CFU/g (mL)	GB4789.10, second method	-
	Vibrio parahaemolyticus	5	1	100 MPN/g (mL)	1000 MPN/g (mL)	GB4789.7	Only applies to aquatic dressing
Nuts and seed products	Salmonella	5	0	0	-	GB4789.4	
	Paste (sauce) of nuts and seeds						
Preserved nuts							

Note 1: the food categories are used to define the scope for applying the pathogen limits; (the categories) are only effective in this standard;

Note 2: "n" is the number of samples taken in one batch of products; "c" is the maximum number of samples allowed over the "m" value; "m" is the tolerant limit of pathogen indexes; M is the highest safe limit of the pathogen indexes.